

HUMAN HISTOPLASMOSIS IN THE *CONUS MEDULLARIS*: ONE CASE FROM ANZOÁTEGUI-VENEZUELA

HISTOPLASMOSIS HUMANA EN EL CONO MEDULAR: UN CASO DE ANZOÁTEGUI-VENEZUELA

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ABSTRACT

A case of histoplasmosis in the *conus medullaris* in a patient from Anzoátegui state, Venezuela is reported. Neurohistoplasmosis is particularly rare in immunocompetent individuals, since progressive disseminated histoplasmosis in the central nervous system occurs in 5-10% of cases. The patient was male, 20 years old, immunocompetent, with a history of hunting and livestock activities. He had no history of respiratory disease. Current disease characterized by axial low back pain and isolated febrile episodes; the patient self-medicated with standard non-steroidal anti-inflammatory and antipyretic drugs without satisfactory evolution. The patient's condition worsened until he was unable to walk or remain in a prolonged standing posture. Neuroimaging reported a single injury in the *conus medullaris* and marked eosinophilia in clinical evaluations paralleled. Due to increasing neurological deficit, the surgical removal of the space-occupying granulomatous lesion was performed, and a biopsy was taken. Histological sections were stained with PAS, Grocott, and H-E, and a bone marrow aspirate smear was stained with Giemsa. The tests revealed structures compatible with *Histoplasma capsulatum*. One sequential treatment with antifungal drugs was applied. Histoplasmosis in the *conus medullaris* is infrequent in other Latin American countries, and this is the first case reported for Venezuela. The histological sections and bone marrow smears provided a conclusive diagnosis of this pathology.

KEY WORDS: Neurohistoplasmosis, medullary cone, *Histoplasma capsulatum*.

RESUMEN

Reportamos un caso de histoplasmosis en el cono medular en un paciente del estado Anzoátegui, Venezuela. La neurohistoplasmosis es particularmente rara en individuos inmunocompetentes, por lo que la histoplasmosis diseminada progresiva en el sistema nervioso central ocurre en el 5-10% de los casos. El paciente era masculino, 20 años, inmunocompetente, con antecedentes de actividades cinegéticas y ganaderas, sin antecedentes de enfermedad respiratoria. La enfermedad actual estuvo caracterizada por dolor lumbar axial y episodios febriles aislados; el paciente se automedicó con antiinflamatorios no esteroideos y antipiréticos estándar sin evolución satisfactoria. El estado del paciente empeoró hasta perder la capacidad de caminar o permanecer en una postura erguida prolongada. La neuroimagen reportó una lesión única en el cono medular y marcada eosinofilia en evaluaciones clínicas paralelas. Debido al aumento del déficit neurológico, se realizó la extirpación quirúrgica de la lesión granulomatosa ocupante de espacio y se tomó una biopsia. Las secciones histológicas se tiñeron con PAS, Grocott y H-E y un frotis de aspirado de médula ósea se tiñó con Giemsa. Las pruebas revelaron estructuras compatibles con *Histoplasma capsulatum*. Se aplicó un tratamiento secuencial con fármacos antifúngicos. La histoplasmosis en el cono medular es poco frecuente en otros países de América Latina y este es el primer caso reportado para Venezuela. Los cortes histológicos y los frotis de médula ósea proporcionaron un diagnóstico concluyente de esta patología.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Neurohistoplasmosis, *conus medullaris*, *Histoplasma capsulatum*.

Histoplasmosis is a systemic granulomatous mycosis, caused by *Histoplasma capsulatum*, a dimorphic fungus with a sapro biogeophilic mycelial phase (infective form) associated with the droppings of bats and birds. This converts to the yeast phase (parasitic form), which is potentially

virulent and often found within mammalian phagocytes. The disease is endemic in several regions of America especially in the valleys bordering the Mississippi and Ohio rivers in the United States (González-González *et al.* 2012). Other important endemic areas were located

including Venezuela in South America, where conditions of temperature and humidity facilitate its development. It also described the disease in Asia, Australia and Oceania (Acuña *et al.* 2008, Colombo *et al.* 2011, Araujo *et al.* 2013).

The mycosis can be acquired by inhalation of microconidias from the ground, initiating primarily in the lungs before spreading to different organs. Clinically, patients may be asymptomatic, or show an acute or chronic primary lung or cutaneous infection with secondary disseminated forms. There are two strains of *Histoplasma* pathogenic to humans, *H. capsulatum* var. *capsulatum*, which produces classical histoplasmosis in America and *H. capsulatum* var. *duboisii*, which only occurs in Africa. Another variety, *H. farsimosum*, is the causal agent of epizootic lymphangitis in equines (Díaz *et al.* 2001).

The interactions that take place between the host and certain species of fungal pathogens lead to a series of events in both. In the hosts, molecules of various types are expressed, some of which participate in the activation of mechanisms that attack and eliminate the invader. Pathogens also express molecules, some of which are morphotype-specific, that help them evade the host defense mechanisms and thus survive within the host (Ortega *et al.* 2010).

Case report

One Venezuelan student male, 20 years old, from “El Milagro” county, Anzoátegui state-Venezuela (8° 53'52. 66"N, 64° 14'51. 73"W), was referring periodical hunter and livestock activities. The man was hunting armadillos (*Dasypos novemcinctus*) and pacas (*Cuniculus paca*) in their caves and working in poultry of roosters (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) and pigeon (*Columba livia*) in near contact with coconut palms (*Coccus nucifera*) and other fruit trees that provide shelter and food for bats (*Desmodus rotundus*). The patient had direct contact with the droppings of these animals.

Symptoms began in June 2013, characterized by non-radiating axial low back pain accompanied by isolated fevers (39°C). The man was self-medicated with non-steroid anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) without satisfactory evolution, worsening to a state where his ability to walk or remain in a prolonged posture was limited. At this point, he was admitted to the local hospital “Dr. Luis Razetti”-Barcelona-Anzoátegui, where he remained for 72 hours in

intense pain in lumbar region, showing no response to common intravenous analgesics (Ketoprofen).

A routine physical examination was undertaken observing that the patient was in a dorsal *de cubitus* position with limited ability to sit up or walk. Heart sounds were regular and rhythmic, without heart murmurs or a gallop rhythm. Respiratory sounds were normal and both lung fields no shown adventitious sounds.

One acupuncture pain in the dorso-lumbar region, was accompanied with abdomen flat, with hydro-aerial sounds, localized left inguinal adenopathy, progressive spastic paraparesis, walking difficulties, anal perineal and scrotal hypoesthesia (saddle hypoesthesia), without compromise of the sphincter function, urinary retention or residual incontinence. The lower limbs were presents as normotonic, with bilateral aquilian hyperreflexia, without clonus or Babinski sign.

Peripheral blood was obtained from antero-brachial region by puncture, with the consequent results: hemoglobin 12.8 g/dL, hematocrit 38%, platelets 250.000 cc, leukocytes 5000 cc, PMN 63%, Linf. 30%, Eos. 2%, Glycemia: 90 mg/dL, Urea 30 mg/dL, Creatinine 0.7 mg/dL, Electrolytes as Na 135 mEq/L, K 3,8 mE/L, Cl 98 mmol/L. HIV antibodies were non-reactive. Serological tests for the identification of toxoplasmosis, paracoccidioidomycosis and histoplasmosis gave negative results.

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) of the dorso-lumbar column revealed several lesion: the T1-weighted sagittal sequence showed an intrathecal-epidural space occupying lesion (SOL), with a lobulated lesion (T12-L1), so intense, heterogeneous and encapsulated, compressing the *conus medullaris* from the back to the front, without obstructing the foramen. After contrast enhancement, the T2-weighted axial sequence (Fig. 1) showed a hyper-intense image with a view of the lesion lateral to the spinal cord; brain magnetic resonance imaging within normal limits. High-resolution tomography of the thorax did not reveal any pathologies. With abdominal/pelvic sonographic measurements within normal limits.

Neuroimagen reveals a possible diagnosis of *conus medullaris* syndrome and an intrathecal-epidural space-occupying lesion (SOL) and was primary treated with centrally acting analgesics (Tramadol).

Surgery was undertaken in 2013. The patient was placed in a prone *de cubitus* position with genupectoral support and a fluoroscope was used to locate the internal structures of interest. Asepsis-antiseptis of the dorso-lumbar region was undertaken and the sterile field prepared. A medial incision over the spinous processes T11 to L2 was made, layers performed dieresis and a laminectomy (T12-L1) avoiding the lateral articulations was accomplished. Flavectomy showed a 20 x 10 mm purplish, granulomatous, solid space-occupying lesion with an irregular surface. The inferior and superior borders of the lesion were exposed and the lesion was removed in a craniocaudal direction, with rigorous hemostasis. A biopsy was taken and the sample fixed in 10% v/v formalin. Finally, layered closure was performed.

Figure 1. MRI: T1-weighted gadolinium-enhanced sagittal sequence, showing an oval, homogeneous, hypointense lesion with perilesional hyperintensity at T12-L1 level (Right scale).

The biopsy taken from the tumor was sent to the Department of Pathological Anatomy, at the “Dr. Luis Razetti” Hospital, Barcelona, Anzoátegui state. The sample were embedded in paraffin. Histology sections (5 μ m) were obtained with Leica RM2125 microtome and stained with Hematoxiline-Eosine (H-E), periodined *Acid-Schiff*, (PAS) or Grocott (Fig. 2 and 3).

The biopsy showed the presence of a diffusely infiltrated tissue compatible with a neuro ectodermal lesion vs lymphoma: the immunohistochemical study showed focal positive

staining for cytokeratins AE1/AE3 and CD20, multifocal positive staining for CD3 and CD45r and diffuse positive staining for CD68.

However, bone marrow aspirate stained with Giemsa (Fig. 4) revealed the presence of intracellular yeasts at 400 and 1000 X. The yeasts were oval with a clear halo and semi lunar cytoplasm concentrated at one end, compatible with *Histoplasma capsulatum* morphology. This is suggestive of a chronic xanthogranulomatous inflammation, secondary to *Histoplasma* sp. infections.

The patient was currently undergoing prolonged antifungal treatment with satisfactory evolution and reversal of symptoms (Fig. 5), note the expansion of *conus*, post-exeresis of SOL decompression laminectomy and *in situ*. Treatment was based on an initial sequential therapy with conventional Amphotericin B at an initial dose of 0.2 mg/Kg/day iv with a daily increase of 0.1 mg/kg, until to reach 35 mg/Kg/day for 8 weeks, followed by itraconazole 400 mg VO OD for 6 months, all in function to the *Histoplasma* susceptibility.

Figure 5. NMR POT:T1-weighted gadolinium-enhanced sagittal sequence of the region exposed by laminectomy at T12-L1, without evidence of injury (right scale from Image).

Ethical aspects

Informed consent to publish the material was obtained from the patient. Authorization service medical records for review of the requested medical records of patients diagnosed with histoplasmosis in the period ranging from 1999-2009. Confidentiality he was respected stories reviewed. This research was approved by the Bioethics Committee of the Hospital Universitario de Caracas.

Figure 2. (A) Granulomatous inflammation with marked histiocytic infiltrate (black point; H-E 1000X). (B) Multiple yeast like structures suggestive of *Histoplasma* sp. (PAS 1000X). (C) Granulomatous osteomyelitis (Grocott). Small *Histoplasma* sp. yeasts treated with argentic impregnation may be observed (1000X).

Figure 3. (A) Granulomatous osteomyelitis. The trabecular bones are surrounded by lymphohistioplasmacytic inflammatory infiltrates (H-E 1000X). (B) Granulomatous inflammation with marked histiocytic infiltrates (PAS 1000X). (C) Yeast-like structures with budding histoplasma.(Grocott 1000X).

Figure 4. (A) Small intracellular *Histoplasma* sp. yeasts in a bone marrow smear (Giemsa 1000X). (B) Intracellular yeast like *Histoplasma* sp. structures in a bone marrow smear (Giemsa 1000X).

Comments

Histoplasmosis is an infection caused by a diphasic geophilic fungus; *H. capsulatum* isolated from soils, with high concentrations of manure, from poultry and pigeons excretion in breeding areas, peridomiliary caves and niches from bats, armadillos and pacas. All these places have optimum moisture, temperature and essential nutrients for the development of the microorganisms. Once the soil becomes contaminated, the fungus can remain potentially infective over many years (González-González *et al.* 2012). Thus, the epidemiological background of this case report patient (the hunting of armadillos and pacas in caves with direct contact with chicken, pigeon and bat droppings) was determinant (Colombo *et al.* 2011).

This study described a disseminated intrathecal-extramedullary fungal infection of segments T12-L1, compatible with histoplasmosis. *Histoplasma* infection may be due to a disseminated infection or an isolated local infection, or both; in this case may have first occurred as a mild asymptomatic primary lung infection that was controlled by the immune system; with intracellular yeasts persisting in permissive cells.

Nevertheless, the patient did not have respiratory problems by clinical history or image data, thus suggesting one direct point of entry of the pathogen to the host *via* skin lesions with posterior hematogenous dissemination, by one excessive exposure to the infective agent.

According to Zalduondo *et al.* (1996), autopsy studies show that CNS histoplasmosis occurs in 5-10% of cases of disseminated infection, although neurological symptoms are absent in many. The infection of the CNS by *Histoplasma* sp. may occur by hematogenous way as manifestation of a localized or progressive disseminated disease. In the reported patient appeared many cuts and puncture wounds during poaching activities, which could be the port of skin entrance of infectious agent.

Kurowski & Ostapchuk (2002), reported that patients prone to developing disseminated histoplasmosis are usually immunosuppressed and unable to develop effective cell-mediated immunity, such as AIDS patients, transplant recipients, carriers of hematologic diseases and patients receiving tumor necrosis factor antagonists (Etanercept and Amfloximab). In this clinical case, the patient was HIV negative and had not no background of

respiratory problems, without a close relationship between the severity of the clinical condition and the patient immune status.

We agreed with Manning *et al.* (2006), that surgery could be unnecessary and not recommended in the majority of cases of focal lesions in the CNS by *H. capsulatum*. However, surgery may be required in cases of progressive neurological deficit or diagnostic uncertainty, such as this case.

Gasparetto *et al.* (2005), reported that magnetic resonance allowed the detection of hypointense spinal cord lesions on T1 and T2, only that on T2, hyperintensity would be observed on the periphery of these. In isolated tumor lesions, as described for our patient, the differential diagnosis would generally be for a spinal cord tumor. This type of tumor accounts for 2-8% of all tumors of the CNS, with low grade astrocytomas being the most frequent in children and ependymomas in adults.

Although the initial diagnostic impression in the presence of a spinal cord tumor continues to be that of a neoplasm, computerized tomography and nuclear magnetic resonance imaging studies could be non-conclusive and non-specific. The characteristics of the SOL as observed from the neuroimages suggested the presence of a neoplastic tumor, the level of the spinal cord affected does not. This would be, consequently, one rare case of histoplasmosis in the *conus medullaris*, and contrasts with reports of histoplasmosis in the cervical spinal cord, brain (Lizarazo *et al.* 2010) and upper dorsal spinal cord (Manning *et al.* 2006).

Wheat (2003), showed that the diagnosis of histoplasmosis can be made by a culture medium, the staining of peripheral blood, aspiration of the bone marrow or skin biopsy, serological tests for antibodies and the detection of antigens. Biopsies represented the gold standard and with bone marrow smear, enabled in this case to identify the causal agent and begin appropriate treatment.

Several types of CNS lesions have been described with a similar clinical way: trichinoechinococcosis, schistosomiasis, sparganosis, hydatidosis, cysticercosis, epidural tuberculous granuloma, pyogenic or fungal epidural abscesses, malaria, amebiasis, coenurosis, paragonimiasis, trichinosis, filariasis, angiostrongylosis, gnathostomiasis and toxoplasmosis. Fungal infections of the spinal cord are uncommon; it is convenient to remember that

they do occur, when making differential diagnoses of granulomatous lesions.

The monitoring of patients, who have terminated a *Histoplasma* infection, by surgical remoting of lesion, is necessary, in function to the records of recurrence in patients over 40 years (Rappleye & Goldman 2006).

In relation to Lemus-Espinoza & Maniscalchi (2021), it confirms the presence and permanence of systemic mycoses in the state of Anzoátegui, considering said region as a geographically endemic area for histoplasmosis, the main sources of infection are bird and pigeon droppings, as well as incursions into caves. In addition, Cermeño *et al.* (2021), some cases of histoplasmosis were reported in El Tigre (Simón Rodríguez Municipality) in the south of the Anzoátegui state.

Conclusions

Neurohistoplasmosis will continue to be a mycosis of great medical and social interest in the coming years. The case report in reference was of an immunocompetent, HIV negative patient showing that this disease is not necessary related to immunosuppression.

The histological sections of the biopsy of the removed tumor stained with H-E, PAS and Grocott and the bone marrow aspirate smear stained with Giemsa, gave conclusive evidence for the diagnosis of this pathology. After undertaking a comprehensive review of the occurrence of human neurohistoplasmosis in the *conus medullaris* in Venezuela and in particular, in Anzoátegui state, we found no evidence of investigations of histoplasmosis in the spinal cord, therefore we consider this finding can be the first report of such a case in Venezuela.

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